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Evaluation of waste to energy technology for municipal solid waste management: A concise review

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ABSTRACT

The increase in Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) volume coupled with diminishing landfill space and rising environmental concerns has spurred a serious need for innovative waste management solutions. The conversion of waste to energy (WtE) technologies has emerged as a critical component of sustainable M.S.W strategies for waste management, which aid in two capacities; Waste reduction and Energy recovery. This study systematically explores some basic methods in Waste to Energy Technology; Incineration, Anaerobic digestion, Gasification, Pyrolysis, and Landfill. Each technology is analyzed based on the critical metrics that involve efficiency in energy recovery, capital, operating costs, environmental impacts, and contributions to circular economic principles. Through a comprehensive review of current literature and case studies, this evaluation identifies the strengths and weaknesses of each technology. Furthermore, it emphasizes integrating Waste-to-Energy solutions into a broader waste management framework that considers socioeconomic factors and technological advancement.

Keywords: Waste – to-energy (WtE), Incineration, Anaerobic digestion (AD), Landfill gas recovery systems (LFGR), Municipal solid waste (MSW)

1. INTRODUCTION

The methods used for the management of waste affect the release of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in several ways, including methane emissions from landfills. The U.S Environmental Protection Agency estimates that landfill methane accounts for about 4 percent of all U.S. GHG emissions measured in terms of global warming potential (GWP) According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, the waste sector, including solid waste and wastewater, accounts for less than 5% of global GHG emissions. The fourth assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), estimated that mitigation of methane from landfills throughout the world, through collection and control and control could reduce methane emissions from landfills globally by 70% at negative to low cost by 2030. In effect, the IPCC points to waste management methods, widely employed by the United States as evidence of the practices that, if used worldwide, could significantly fight climate change on a global basis.

The rate of the massive increase in the number of persons leaving rural areas for urban regions and the massive increase in industries within the urban settlement has resulted in high challenges in the environment (Dastjerdi, 2019). It was estimated by the study that 1.3 billion tons of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) were generated in the whole world and the study also finds the estimation that the number generated might reach 2.2 billion tons per year by 2025 and likely 4.2 billion tons per year by 2050 (Ram et al 2021). Municipal solid waste management (MSWM) has been a complicated process because it involves collaborative decision-making on selecting waste collection routes, waste transfer stations as well as waste facilities for treatment and strategies from different available options. Selecting a waste treatment strategy has been one of the major issues in the literature and is the core of MSWM. The increase in per capita energy use and the production of waste are two of the largest issues the world is currently experiencing (Hasan, et al 2021). The facilities and strategies for waste treatment mostly consist of landfilling and waste-to-energy (WTE) technologies. In the context of Municipal Solid Waste Management (MSWM), the process of assessing the economic, environmental, and social impact of available waste treatment is referred to as sustainability (Sultani, et al, 2016). To achieve this goal of sustainability in waste management, the practice of waste generation reduction, waste recycling, and recovering of energy for future uses. In South Asia, one of the fastest growing countries in terms of urbanization, Bangladesh has been observed struggling with a sharp increase in energy demand and production and waste production (Pandey, et al 2022). Nearly 42% of the generated MSW in that country is landfilled, and this results in the contamination of surface and groundwater by landfill leachate, unpleasant odors, bioaerosol emissions, and toxic organic compounds (Zhang, et al, 2021).

The country was discovered not to have standard waste management policies, systems, trash collection services, or government institutions to properly manage their waste. In the case of energy generation, Bangladesh is also facing difficulty in bridging the gap between energy demand and supply (Zhang, et al, 2021). The country is highly dependent on imported fossil fuels for electricity production. According to records, Nigeria generates over 32 million tons of solid waste yearly, and only a fraction is collected, mostly these wastes are generated by households and in some cases, by local industries, artisans, and traders who litter the immediate surroundings. Improper collection and disposal of municipal wastes have led to different levels of environmental challenges such as the blockade of sewers, and drain networks and the choking of water bodies (George, 2010).

Waste-to-energy technology (WTE) can be a very suitable form of managing Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) but at the same time challenging across the world due to the facilities involved. Many studies have been laid down on this waste management strategy; a study conducted by Udomsri et al., on the evaluation of municipal solid waste in Thailand to cope with climate change and sustainable direction for the development of biomass-based electricity generation. According to this study, it was formalized that the impact of waste associated with the environment could be mitigated by municipal solid waste (MSW) incineration, whereas this could expand biomass-based energy production positively (Udomsri, 2011). Philip and Mondal studied Municipal Solid Waste in India, with their mathematical framework of sustainability options, they discovered that the gasification technique possesses some potential for being Municipal Solid Waste treatment as a sustainable option. This was because of their overall high impact on local people and their environment (Philip et al., 2014). A study by Kumar reviews the assessment of the performance feasibility of various waste-to-energy technologies which includes; Anaerobic digestion, Gasification, and incineration.

The study found that waste-to-energy technologies can effectively reduce the amount of municipal solid waste sent to landfills, but also highlights the need for careful consideration of environmental and social impacts (Kumar, 2014). Singh, studies waste-to-energy technologies for municipal solid waste management, using Delhi in India as a case study, His study evaluates the potential of waste-to-energy technologies in Delhi, India, where municipal solid waste management was a serious challenge. His study found that waste-to-energy technologies can reduce greenhouse gas emissions and generate electricity, but he also notes that there should be a need for more effective waste segregation and collection systems to support these technologies. (Zhang, 2020) studies, assessed the techno-economic evaluation of waste-to-energy technologies for municipal solid waste. His evaluation assesses the viability of the economics of various waste-to-energy technologies such as anaerobic digestion, incineration, and gasification. His study finds that above all, anaerobic digestion happens to be the most cost-effective option, followed by gasification and incineration. His study concluded by highlighting the importance of considering economic factors in addition to environmental and social impacts in the decision-making process (Zhang, 2020). Ahsan carried out a critical review of the environmental impacts of different waste-to-energy technologies. His review examines various environmental impacts of waste to energy, such as air pollution, water pollution, and land use changes. The study concluded that waste-to-energy technologies have significant benefits attached, but they also pose a significant environmental risk if poorly implemented, highlighting the need for more rigorous monitoring and regulations (Athanasidou, 2015).

2. THE HIERARCHY IN WASTE MANAGEMENT

The hierarchy depicts the best solution for managing waste according to the best method that is suitable for a particular environment (Figure 1).

2.1. Prevention

Based on hierarchy, priority should be given to waste prevention which includes making use of fewer materials, reducing waste at source, and keeping it for longer. Prevention of waste is more advantageous compared to any waste management strategies like energy recovery, recycling, landfill, etc. This is because the materials or products that result in waste are

circumvented (Awasthi MK, 2020). According to the World Bank report, the easiest way to manage or reduce waste is to reduce or minimize economic activities. This is because when countries urbanize, their standard of living grows along with their economic wealth, disposable income, and consumption of goods and services which leads to an increase in waste generation. Another way to prevent this waste is by moving from a linear to a circular economy, such as curtailing resource extraction and material input as well as improving efficiency through developmental design, recycling, and collections.

Figure 1. The hierarchy of waste management

2. 2. Recycle or Reuse

This involves fixing, repairing, and using the material not necessarily for the purpose it was meant for, but for another useful purpose. In this way, useless waste is converted into useful material or product, while hazardous into harmless material hence improving utilization. When waste is recycled, economic, social, and environmental benefits are promoted (Awasthi, 2019). This is because countries save natural resources, decrease energy consumption, and promote employment while decreasing waste pollution. Recycling plays a crucial role in sustainability, but it alone is insufficient to establish a truly sustainable economy. As a downstream process addressing waste after its generation, recycling serves as the last resort in the circular economy strategy. The circular economy is a comprehensive economic system aiming to eliminate waste and promote the continuous use of resources (Jing et al, 2023).

2. 3. Recovery

This stage involves the recovery of usefulness from the waste through energy recovery techniques such as anaerobic digestion, fermentation, incineration, gasification, and pyrolysis to produce energy (fuel, heat, and power), and using waste for backfilling. The recovery of biogas and heat energy from landfills and incineration plants, respectively, will reduce waste generation and help in the appropriate reutilization of resources. Resource utilization of livestock and manure, agricultural waste, domestic sewage sludge, and other organic SWs

during aerobic composting and anaerobic digestion and then recycling the organic substances and nutrients, etc. are some of the efficient ways to realize SW resources and materials recovery systems (Awasthi, 2019).

2. 4. Disposal

Figure 2. Open Disposal of Waste (open dumping)

In developing countries, open dumpsites are common, due to the low budget for waste disposal and non-availability of trained manpower. Open dumping of MSW is a common practice in developing countries. It also poses a serious threat to groundwater resources and soil. The contamination of soil by heavy metals can cause adverse effects on human health, animals, and soil productivity. Over the years, heavy metals have considerably damaged soil quality and fertility as a consequence of increased environmental pollution from industrial, agricultural, and municipal sources. Metals cause physiological disorders in soils as absorption through the root system, consequently, retard retards plant growth and deprives it of vigor (Syeda et al, 2014).

In most countries, waste is disposed of through grinding, milling, open dumping, landfilling, and compaction or burned in an incinerator without energy recovery, based on the country's policies. This same waste can also be disposed of in other countries only when it has a market in those specific countries. In countries where the incomes are high, waste is mostly disposed of through landfilling and thermal treatments while the middle- and low-income countries are mostly disposed of by open dumping and poorly managed landfilling. However, the middle-income countries operate with managed dumping processes.

2. 5. Waste-to-energy technology processes

WtE could be referred to as an established option for municipal solid waste treatment and is aimed both to minimize environmental stresses as well as increase the share of renewable energy (Athanasidou et al., 2015). In the past decade, WtE plants have been seriously criticized for being negatively impacted on the environment as well affect public health, but in actual reality, they are equipped with sophisticated air pollution control (APC) systems that help to mitigate air pollutant emissions, which are strictly monitored. Directive 2000/76/EC on the incineration of waste, made WtE one of the most stringently regulated and controlled industrial activities. Waste to Energy (WtE) has developed massively in the past two decades in areas such as Europe, North America, and Asia with well-improved technologies which happen to be among the cleanest sources of thermoelectric energy.

So far, the dominant WtE technology is by grate combustion of "as-received or post-recycling" MSW used for the production of electricity and heat as well. This is practically practiced in over 200 plants in over 45 nations. Today, the combustion process is seen as the most dominant and also proven waste-to-energy (WtE) technology, having more than 2000 well-operating plants worldwide. Globally, the facilities of WtE can treat more than 250 million tons annually, and the forecasts from both the International Solid Waste Association and the United Nations Environment Program estimate this capacity to increase by 500% in the next decade, as many of the worldwide developing nations embrace WtE technology to reduce their reliance on landfills and dumpsites strongly (Gohlke, 2009).

2. 6. Waste to energy plant layout

Key components of waste-to-energy (WtE) plant layout include; a bunker, combustion chamber, boiler, steam turbine/generator, air pollution control (APC), and stack.

From the weighbridge, vehicles proceed to the tipping hall to discharge their load into the waste bunker. There are tipping bays into which the vehicles reverse. The bays are demarcated with bollards and raised kerbs to allow the vehicles to reverse safely. The tipping hall is fitted with a roller shutter door to minimize fugitive emissions of odor.

This door remains closed when no waste deliveries are occurring. The tipping hall is also maintained at low pressure to further minimize odor emissions, and it is cleaned periodically. A sloping floor allows wastewater produced by cleaning activities to be collected for further treatment.

2. 6. 1. Bunker

Above the waste bunker, there are installed sets of automatic control grabs mounted on traveling cranes. They are operated by crane operators seated in the control room overlooking the waste bunker. Control can be manual, semi-automatic, or fully automatic. In addition to feeding the charging hoppers, cranes mix the waste in the bunker. Mixing of the waste ensures good consistency and improves combustion. The capacity of the grab is sufficiently large to feed the charging hoppers while operating at full capacity.

The weight of the waste in the grab is recorded automatically, and the data are fed back to the control room. The waste bunker also serves as a temporary storage area during periods of maintenance or shutdown.

The bunker usually can store 4–7 days' worth of waste at normal operating capacity. In case of a prolonged shutdown, waste can be transferred from the bunker back into Lorries for safe disposal in a licensed facility.

During normal operation, the bunker is emptied in a rotation sequence to prevent long periods where waste remains in certain parts, which could result in waste degradation and odor production. The bunker is equipped with a system for continuous monitoring of excessive heat within the waste. This consists mainly of an infrared camera mounted within the bunker.

Figure 3(a,b). a) Indicative waste reception Bunker, b) Indicative waste reception Bunker and the crane.

2. 6. 2. Combustion Chamber

To ensure steady combustion conditions. The following three combustion chambers/systems are applicable in WtE plants, with the first one being the most prevailing and most popular due to simplicity of operation: moving grates, rotary kiln, and fluidized bed.

2. 6. 3. Moving grates combustion

Conventional moving grate combustion consists of a layer on the grate, transporting material through the furnace. While on the grate, the waste is Cranes transfer waste from the waste bunker into the feed system, which consists of feeding hoppers and chutes that feed the combustion chamber. The charging hopper aims to feed the waste continuously and smoothly dried and burned at high temperatures with air supply. The ash (including non-combustible fractions of Waste) leaves the grate as slag/bottom ash through the ash chute. The grate forms the bottom of the furnace. The moving grate, if properly designed, efficiently transports and agitates the waste and evenly distributes the combustion air. The grate may be sectioned into individually adjustable zones, and the combustion air can usually be preheated to accommodate variations in the lower calorific value of the waste. The potential advantages of this are lower dust carry-over in the flue gases, lower bed temperature (and therefore lower NO_x formation in the bed), simplified gas-treatment procedures and lower running cost among others. The major disadvantages are, however, reduced throughput, of the waste and possibly higher carbon in the ash at exist (Yao et al, 2007).

2. 6. 4. Rotary Kiln

Rotary kiln systems are widely used in industrial applications to transfer energy from high temperature flames to irregular solids. These systems are suitable for the incineration of hazardous solid waste materials and thermal treatment of contaminated soils (Lemieux and Pershing, 1989). Combustion based on a rotary kiln consists of a layered burning of the waste in a rotating cylinder. The material is transported through the furnace by the rotations of the inclined cylinder. The rotary kiln is usually refractory-lined but can also be equipped with water walls. The cylinder may be 1–5 meters in diameter and 8–20 meters long. The capacity may be as low as 2.4 t/day (0.1 t/hour) and up to approximately 480 t/day (20 t/hour). The excess air ratio is well above that of the moving grate combustor and even the fluidized bed. Consequently, the energy efficiency is slightly lower and may be up to 80%. As the retention time of flue gases is usually too short for a complete reaction in the rotary kiln itself, the cylinder is followed by, and connected to, an after-burning chamber, which can be incorporated into the first part of the boiler. The current hazardous waste treatment methods mainly include incineration and landfill. Rotary kiln incineration is highly adaptable and can burn combustible materials of different states and shapes. Rotary kiln incineration operation is simple, easier to control, long service life, and good continuous work (Liu et al, 2020)

2. 6. 5. Fluidized Bed Combustion

Fluidized bed has high efficiency and Super heaters in the circulation loop (Bo and Fredrik, 2020). A wide variety of waste has been burned in the fluidized-bed incinerators including municipal solid waste, Agricultural waste, coal mine waste, waste oils, and sludges, wood wastes, petroleum refinery wastes, petrochemicals waste, etc. (Saxena and Jotshi, 1994). The fluidized bed combustion process is based on the principle whereby solid particles are

mixed with fluid and fluidized by air. The disadvantage of this fluidized bed for waste combustion, is usually the demanding process of pretreating waste before the fluidized bed, to meet the rather stringent requirements for size, calorific value, ash content, etc. Because of the heterogeneous composition of MSW, it can be challenging to produce a fuel that meets the requirements at any given point.

2. 7. Typical chemistry of waste-to-energy technology

(I) flow Chart of waste to energy by incinerator

(II) flow Chart of waste to energy by gassification

(III) flow Chart of waste to energy by Anaerobic digestion

(IV) flow Chart of Land fill to gas energy

Figure 4. Schematic representation of incineration, Gasification, Anaerobic Digestion, and Landfill Gas, WtE.

Waste-to-energy (WtE) technology is the process of converting non-recyclable waste materials into usable forms of energy. Primarily, electricity, heat, or fuel through various methods. The chemistry involved in waste to energy process, encompasses several complex reactions, depending on the technology used. The primary methods for waste-to-energy conversion include; Incineration, anaerobic, gasification, pyrolysis, and landfill (Figure 4).

2. 7. 1. Incineration

Incineration is one of the most common methods of WtE and involves the combination of organic materials at high temperatures. The chemical reactions during this process include the following reactions.

2. 7. 2. Combustion Reaction

In combustion reaction, organic waste, mainly composed of carbon (C), Hydrogen (H), Sulfur (S), etc. undergoes combustion in the presence of oxygen (O₂), Producing Carbon dioxide (CO₂), and water (H₂O) and various other gases example SO₂ from sulfur-containing compounds.

2. 7. 3. Ash Formation

Inorganic materials such as metals and minerals do not combust and instead form ash, which requires proper disposal. Fe₂O₃, MnO, Na₂CO₃, NaHCO₃ etc. (Marco et al, 2019).

2. 8. Anaerobic Digestion

This refers to a biological process that breaks down organic matter in the absence of oxygen, typically using microorganisms. The main chemical reaction in stages.

2. 8. 1. Hydrolysis

Here complex organic materials (Proteins, Carbohydrates, fats) are broken down into simpler compounds example; amino acid, Sugars, and fatty acids.

2. 8. 2. Acidogenesis

In acidogenesis, simple compounds are further fermented into volatile fatty acids, hydrogen (H), and Carbon dioxide (CO₂). Acidogenesis is the fermentation stage where the products of hydrolysis (soluble organic monomers of sugars and amino acids) are degraded by

acidogenic bacteria to produce alcohols, aldehydes, and volatile fatty acids (VFAs) and acetate together with H₂ and CO₂ (Sambusiti, 2013).

2. 9. Pyrolysis and Gasification

Pyrolysis is a chemical transformation process that involves a destructive distillation process in an oxygen-deficient environment. The resulting product includes:

(a) A solid residue (b) a liquid component and (c) a gaseous byproduct. An example of this process is the pyrolysis of cellulose which can be described by the following chemical equation:

In the case above, the solid product is carbon, the liquid component is ethylene and the resulting gas is methane. Each of these substances can be used as fuel. A variation of pyrolysis is gasification. Gasification allows the conversion of MSW into gaseous fuel (syngas) that can be used in gas engines, combined cycle gas turbines, and solid gas fuel cells (Cristhian et al, 2024). In gasification, a limited amount of oxygen is supplied, either in the form of pure oxygen or air. During the subsequent oxidation, sufficient heat is generated to maintain the system independently. Consequently, depending on the amount of heat and oxygen supplied, the reaction can be either exothermic or endothermic. The temperature range used during the pyrolysis process varies between 300 °C and 900 °C, with more typical ranges being between 500 °C and 550 °C. At these temperatures, liquid products represent the major portion of products, whereas at higher temperatures the major product is gas. Pyrolysis of municipal solid waste was believed to hold great potential, since it is a process with virtually no emissions, thus, having an excellent environmental profile, which produces several useful fuels. This is the reason several studies have been performed to determine the pyrolysis behavior of several components of municipal solid waste (Luka et al, 2023).

2. 10. Landfill gas capture and utilization

A Landfill can be defined as a scientific dumping of MSW using an Engineering facility which requires detailed planning and specification, careful construction, and efficient operation (Tozlu et al, 2016). It is one of the most widely used approaches for waste treatment in developing countries. It can also be defined as the disposal of wastes on land and can produce biogas also known as landfill gas (LFG) (Dastjerdi et al, 2019). Landfill gas capture and utilization as a technology and equipment as a whole is used for capturing and utilizing landfill gas for different applications such as electricity, thermal generation, and fuels. Landfill gas capture and utilization play a crucial role in reducing methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, which can adversely affect the environment (Sieting et al, 2014).

When municipal solid waste (MSW) is buried in a landfill, a complex series of reactions occur in which anaerobic microorganisms decompose a portion of the organic fraction of the waste to carbon dioxide and methane. The methane produced may be collected and flared or converted to energy, which oxidizes the methane to carbon dioxide. The methane can also be oxidized to carbon dioxide by methanotrophic bacteria in the landfill cover soil. Therefore, the ultimate fate of carbon placed in the landfill is sequestered or emitted as methane or carbon dioxide. In terms of atmospheric, methane from landfills is considered an anthropogenic source

of carbon while carbon dioxide is considered biogenic in origin and not an anthropogenic source (Tozlu et al, 2016).

2. 11. MSW Generation input: Current Status and Future Prediction

Municipal solid waste generation in terms of quantity and future forecast is of great importance for the planning of waste management systems. Various reports have shown that increases in the quantity of waste generation worldwide have resulted from the rise in population, urbanization, living standards, and industrialization in and around towns. Thus, every individual is affected by solid waste generation directly or indirectly.

Table 1. MSW generation in different countries (Ram, et al, 2019).

S/No	Country	Waste generation (million Metric tons per year)
1	United States	258
2	China	220.4
3	India	168.4
4	Brazil	79.89
5	Indonesia	65.2
6	Russia	60
7	Mexico	53.1
8	Germany	51.05
9	Japan	43.98
10	France	33.4
11	United Kingdom	31.57
12	Turkey	31.28
13	Pakistan	30.76
14	Nigeria	27.61
15	Canada	25.1
16	South Africa	18.46
17	Korea	18.22
18	Argentina	17.91
19	Saudi Arabia	16.13
20	Australia	13.35

Research from China reflects that the total amount of solid waste generation has risen for almost all 651 cities from 2007 to 2016. China shows an annual per capita municipal solid waste generation (MSWG) that is greatly varying, which indicates that the rising trend of MSWG is full of diversity (Pan et al. 2019).

Developed and developing countries have differences in their lifestyle and development scenarios, which ultimately are responsible for the quantity of solid waste generation and its characteristics. The developed countries typically generate an average of 522.0 to 759.2 kg per capita per year (kcy), which is generally higher than the 109.5 to 525.6 kcy typically by developing countries (Karak et al., 2012).

A study from 15 countries of the European Union (EU-15) indicated that the average MSW generation increased in the EU-15 by 4.6% from 540-565 kcy from 1998 to 2008. Among the EU-15 in 2008, a considerably higher amount of solid waste generation, i.e. 802 kcy, was observed. However, Greece was observed to generate the lowest rate of MSW, i.e 453 kcy, among the EU-15 in the year 2008. China, delivered a total MSW of approximately 203.62 million tonnes in 2016, an increase of 33.83 % (Ram et al, 2021).

Table 2. Global populations and MSW Generation in Various Countries (Ram et al, 2021).

S.No.	Country	Share of global Population (%)	Share of global MSW (%)
1	China	18.75	15.55
2	India	18.05	11.95
3	United States	4.4	11.65
4	Indonesia	3.55	3.30
5	Brazil	2.8	3.85
6	Russia	1.95	2.4
7	Japan	1.70	2.15
8	Germany	1.15	1.95
9	United Kingdom	0.90	1.50
10	South Africa	0.75	0.70
11	Canada	0.45	1.40
12	Saudi Arabia	0.45	0.75
13	Australia	0.35	0.75

About 3.40 billion tonnes in 2050 which is 70% higher than 2016 levels. The World Bank initiative is ambitious to combat the waste management problem. For this purpose, the World Bank, spent over \$4.7 billion for more than 340 solid waste management programs. MSW generation is the status of worldwide solid waste management generation is around 2.01 billion tonnes as of 2016 amounting to a footprint of 0.74kg per capita per day. Furthermore, with the fast-growing populations and the urbanization sector, the annual solid waste generation rate is expected to increase to about predicted to exceed the rate of urbanization in 2025, and in the coming decades the total MSW generation rate in developing countries will also increase rapidly (Ram et al, 2021)

3. WASTE-TO-ENERGY TECHNOLOGY

Waste-to-Energy (WtE) technology utilizes municipal solid waste (MSW) to generate energy in the form of electricity, heat, or biofuels. This review evaluates various WtE technologies, their performance, environmental impacts, as well as the current trends and future directions in the field. The major challenge and success of WtE technology depends on the efficiency, technical, environmental, and economic feasibility. The table below shows the analysis of different WtE technologies. In the table, the comparison is made between different WtE technologies but, a real comparison requires a detailed life cycle assessment of each technology.

Incineration technology is most widely known and used commercially to combust for energy production in the form of heat, electricity, or both. This is due to lower annual capital and operational costs as seen in the table below, with less complex technology making it easier to operate, high efficiency, and quick process, dealing with different types of waste and reducing volume by approximately 80% and mass by approximate 70% of waste. However, it produces pollutants in both solid (Highly leachable fly ash and bottom ash) and gaseous (NO_x, and SO_x and formation of halogenated hydrocarbons). Therefore, air pollution control devices such as fabric filters, desulfurization, NO_x abatement activated carbon injection, etc., and immobilization of solid waste make it environmentally safe for landfill disposal.

Gasification technology holds a promising and sustainable energy future but faces challenges that need to be addressed through innovation, investment, and supportive policies. Its versatility and potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (meeting existing emission limits) make it an area of significant interest in the context of energy transition and resource recovery. This technology is widely used in Japan, where 85 plants were operating till 2007, and around 100 plants globally, which is a relatively low number of plants worldwide that are operating commercially.

Gasification/Pyrolysis has certain advantages over incineration due to its fewer greenhouse emissions, less energy required in flue gas cleaning, reducing waste volume by 95%, and modern gasification units come with enclosure, which effectively reduces the chance of soil and water contamination, however, technical and economic issues, mainly related to the homogeneity of wastes(used tires, papers, electrical waste), power efficiency of plants and syngas cleaning system, high operating, and capital costs compare to incineration plants as a result of ash melting in gasifiers or treatment of solid waste or water waste in pyrolysis, are a hurdle for gasification /pyrolysis technologies to be established commercially all over the world.

Table 3. Economic and environmental factor comparison of WtE technologies (Shahmir and Saifullah, 2018).

Type of Technology	Type of waste	Capital cost (US\$/tonne of waste/year)	Operational cost (US\$/tonne of waste/year)	Global warming potential m(kg CO ₂ Equivalent per unit MWh electricity generation)	Complexity of Technology	Labour Skill Level
Incineration	General	400-700	40-70	424	Low	Low
Pyrolysis	Homogenous	400-700	50-80	412	High	Intermediate
Gasification	Homogenous	250-850	45-85	412	High	Intermediate
Anaerobic digestion	Organic	50-350	5-35	222	Low	Low
Landfilling with gas Recovery	Inert	10-30	1-3	746(if gases are not recovered)	Low	Low

The anaerobic digestion process has the lowest capital and operating cost as shown in Table 3, compared to incineration and thermal conversion technologies. The closed system makes it compact and promotes the use of this technology at a small scale in rural areas. Anaerobic digestion offers lots of advantages as it is a renewable source of energy producing small amounts of solid (which can be used as fertilizer), reducing odors, and producing an important fuel known as biogas. Production of biogas from anaerobic digestion is faster, as it is reported that it can produce 2-4 times more in 3 weeks than landfill gas technique in 6-7 years. Although its waste treatment is slower compared to thermal conversion (typically 20-40 of bacteria reactions), the plant has higher space requirements and it is sensitive to process parameters like an increase in ammonia and salt concentrations which can stop the methanogenesis process due to the presence of nitrogen-rich compounds and cations (Sodium, potassium, and calcium).

Landfill is mostly favorable in some developing countries because it is the least expensive process as seen in Table 3. Biogas produced can have a variety of applications, skilled labor is not required, returning natural resources to the soil, and the conversion of marshy lands into useful areas. Its disadvantage is that it requires a high cost for transporting the waste, and requires a large area, it adversely impacts the environment, as it risks the contamination of groundwater or water streams nearby by leachate, it has a very slow process, with the highest greenhouse emissions (as methane has 21 time more global warming potential than CO₂) and possibly fire/explosion due to production of methane (if not trapped and used/flared). This method is, however, made environmentally friendly by using inert waste and the biogas produced. Biogas produced can be stored and used for electricity and/heat or biofuels in transport using the already present nature of gas infrastructure. Since it is a renewable source of energy, it can reduce the load on fossil fuels. For more commercial use, the quality of biogas can be improved by removing carbon dioxide and other trace gases.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation of waste-to-energy (WtE) technologies is an area of increasing research importance as countries seek sustainable solutions to manage waste and generate renewable energy. MSW management has become a valuable alternative for some developed nations but remains challenging for most developing countries. Despite significant advancements, there are still several research gaps that need to be addressed. The existing research gaps are thus; Life cycle assessment (LCA), Energy and Material Recovery, Emerging contaminants, Integration with Circular Economy, Public Perception and Acceptance, Socio-economic Impacts, etc. Modern waste-to-energy (WTE) facilities do not only fulfill the original goals of waste management such as waste reduction and sanitization, but also play an important role in conserving resources, producing energy, and meeting environmental protection needs. The evaluation of waste-to-energy (WTE) technologies as a strategy for municipal solid waste (MSW) management addresses the urgent need to manage the rise in waste volume sustainability. Despite significant advancements, there are still several research gaps that need to be addressed.

The existing research gaps are thus; Life cycle assessment (LCA), Energy and Material Recovery, Emerging contaminants, Integration with Circular Economy, Public Perception and Acceptance, Socio-economic Impacts, etc. Incineration may be widely utilized for its ability to reduce the waste volume significantly as well as generate energy. However, it raises a concern about air pollution and ash disposal. Anaerobic digestion simply converts organic waste into biogas, which can be utilized for energy generation, contributing to waste reduction and nutrient recovery. Gasification and pyrolysis though less common offer potential advantages such as lower emissions and a higher energy yield from biomass. The study underscores the necessity of considering local contexts, regulatory frameworks, and community acceptance in implementing Waste to Energy technologies. It advocates for a holistic approach, integrating waste to energy within broader waste management systems to optimize resource recovery and as well minimize environmental impacts. Therefore, advancing waste-to-energy technologies can play a significant role in improving sustainable waste management practices, and energy production and reducing dependence on fossil fuels, thereby supporting environmental sustainability goals.

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